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Introduction: The Umayyads from West to East: New Perspectives

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This special issue arose out of a conference hosted by the RomanIslam Center for Comparative Empire and Transcultural Studies (Universität Hamburg) in March 2021. The conference, entitled “The Umayyads from West to East: New Perspectives” focused on intra-Empire comparison between the Umayyads of the West and the East and on the relevance of various Roman and Late Antique contexts to the conceptualization of Umayyad rule. However, the lens through which most contributors chose to analyze this question, and a recurring topic in the subsequent discussions, was the relevance of transregional Umayyad memory, particularly from the perspective of the Islamic West. The entries in this volume are grouped around this focus, examining different ways in which transregional Umayyad memories influenced, and were influenced by, the culture of the Islamic West.

Mnemohistory, or the study of the past as it was remembered, constructed, and recontextualized, has been a thriving area of inquiry in the humanities since the studies of Maurice HALBWACHS (1939) on collective memory and those by Aleida and Jan ASSMANN (1992, 2012) on cultural memory more specifically.¹ Its impact on the study of Islamic history has been significant and has led to important advances in the field. Particularly prominent studies include Antoine BORRUT’s analysis of Umayyad memories in Syria (2011),² Sarah SAVANT’s book on pre-Islamic memories in Iran (2013), Heather KEANEY’s work on the remembrance of the rebellion against ‘Uthmān, and Tayeb EL-HIBRI’s research on the memories of the Rāshidūn (2010) and the Umayyad rulers (2002). The instrumentalization of the past is also an important topic in the studies of early Islamic historiography by Boaz SHOSHAN (2016), Fred DONNER (1998), and more recently, in Manan AHMED ASIF’s study of the *Chachnama* and its creative context (2016).

1 For a survey of the field, see ERLI and NÜNNING 2008.

2 See also the collected volume edited by Antoine BORRUT and Paul COBB (2010).

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Less attention to memory is evident in historical studies of the Islamic West. However, for this region too, studies have shown its relevance to almost all aspects of Umayyad culture. The research of Gabriel MARTÍNEZ GROS (1992), Janina SAFRAN (2000), and Maribel FIERRO (2011) highlights the ideological implications of the discourse of legitimacy in the Umayyad caliphate of Cordoba and its historical references,³ while the relevance of the past to the artistic legacy of the Umayyads has been addressed by Susana CALVO CAPILLA and Jorge ELICES OCÓN (2010, 2018, 2021). So too have Antonio VALLEJO's studies on the Umayyad caliphal architecture of Madīnat al-Zahrā' demonstrated the importance of the Umayyad heritage in the building of the new city, where the two main halls of receptions represented the Umayyad rights over the East and the West (2010, 2016). The political relevance of the past to the Umayyads' present has been analyzed by Eduardo MANZANO MORENO (2019),⁴ in Javier ALBARRÁN's analysis of the commemoration of historical battles of the Islamic East in al-Andalus (2020, 2021), and most recently, in Elsa CARDOSO's study of the legitimizing role of court concepts in Umayyad Cordoba (2023).

Umayyad memories have played an important role in both the eastern and western stretches of the Islamic Realm, where their relevance for transregional relations has been twofold. One important use of memory is as a formative, and often legitimizing, element in the political, intellectual, and artistic culture of the western Umayyads. How were elements from the Islamic East incorporated into western Umayyad discourse and what different aims were served by the memories associated with these elements? One could widen this question to include the chronological as well as the geographical dimension; how did the western Umayyads invoke the memory of the pre-Islamic Iberian Peninsula to create their own Islamic culture and what does this say about their relationship with their past?

Another, different, use of Umayyad memory in transregional relations is the remembrance of the western Umayyads themselves and the role that this played in forming the cultural and political discourse of the wider Islamic Empire. The historical memory of the Umayyads has long been central for the regional identity of Greater Syria,⁵ where nostalgia for the eastern Umayyads accompanied the marginalization of the region in the first centuries of 'Abbāsīd rule.⁶ This became stronger during the "Sunni revival" of the Middle period, when the Umayyad legacy

3 Umayyad ideology and its reference to the past are also addressed by ALAJMI / KESHK 2013.

4 David WASSERSTEIN (1993) and Francois CLÉMENT (1997) explore various aspects about the survival of the idea of the Umayyad caliphate after 1031.

5 Cf. the various references in Wien (2017), as for instance, to the "Umayyad riots" in Baghdad 1927, p. 44. Cf. also the study by Werner ENDE (1977) on the image of the Umayyads in schoolbooks.

6 PELLAT (1956). See also PETERSEN (1964).

often featured as a historical counterpoint to Shi'ite claims.⁷ This moment coincided with the expansion of Christian kingdoms in Iberia and the increasing emigration of Maghribis and Andalusis to Greater Syria, where their memories about the Cordoban Umayyads enriched knowledge about the distant Islamic West and added a layer of romantic nostalgia.⁸ In the periods after these memories about the eastern and western Umayyad dynasties frequently converged, and even in the 20th century, Arab nationalist and particularly Baathist instrumentalizations of the Umayyad caliphate as embodying Arab glory tended to merge visions of both the eastern and the western dynasties.⁹

Not only in the East but also in the West, the memory of the Umayyad caliphate dominated historical consciousness after the collapse of the regime in 1031. Existing and fictive Umayyad caliphal candidates played an important legitimizing role during the period of the Taifa kingdoms and served to sustain claims of hegemony.¹⁰ In the same period, many Andalusis, anxious about Muslim disunity and the expansion of the Christian kingdoms, hoped for a restitution of a unified Umayyad caliphate. The most prominent representative is the polymath Ibn Ḥazm (d. 1064), who repeatedly advocated in favor of the Umayyad caliphate and whose nostalgic view of past Umayyad glory colors many of his works.¹¹ Later, the Almohads used Umayyad memories and references to underpin their claim of caliphal legitimacy.¹²

Both of these uses of memory were addressed in the conference. Many contributions, and much of the discussion, focused on the construction, implementation, and instrumentalization of Umayyad memories in the Islamic West. What did the western Umayyads know about their eastern ancestors, how did they commemorate and remember them, and what role did these memories play in their self-fashioning and legitimation? Other contributions looked at the memory of the western Umayyads and their integration into later generations' views of a transregional Umayyad continuity.

7 On the interventions of Ṣalāḥ al-Dīn and Nūr al-Dīn in the Damascus urban space, see BURNS (2005), 170–195.

8 POUZET 1975. On the influence of the Maghrib in the Mashriq, see FIERRO / PENELAS (2021).

9 Cf. CIVANTOS 2017, 26, 30, with further references; ENDE 1977. The neoclassic poet and cultural pan-Arabist Ahmad Shawqī, for instance, was an enthusiast of Umayyad al-Andalus and the figure 'Abd al-Raḥmān I.

10 Cf. the studies by David WASSERSTEIN 1993; CLÉMENT 1997. Cf. also the thematic dossier in the journal *Usur al-Wusta* 26, 2018 “Formulating the Caliphate in the West: Umayyads, Hammudids, and Almohads.”

11 MARTINEZ-GROS 2013.

12 ALBARRÁN 2020, 357 ff.

The papers in this special issue represent a good cross-section of the themes developed during and around the conference. Javier ALBARRÁN's contribution highlights the transformation of two emblematic battles associated with the Umayyads of the East into sites of memory in al-Andalus. The first of these, Ḥunayn (8/630), featured the former enemy and subsequently prominent helper of the Prophet, Abū Sufyān, who was the ancestor of the Sufyānid Umayyads. The second, Marj Rāhiṭ (64/684), marked the ascendance of the Marwānid branch of the Umayyads and the defeat of the opposing Zubayrids. ALBARRÁN's article is followed by Sebastian BITSCH's study of an almost uncovered topic, namely the textual and archeological evidence for the *alqāb* (throne-names) attributed to the eastern Umayyads, and their mirroring and replication in the Islamic West. His study opens an intriguing perspective on a cross-cultural phenomenon that evidences the increasing sacralization of political authority since Late Antiquity. Antonia BOSANQUET's article addresses the 'Abbāsīd view of the Umayyads through an analysis of depictions of the "Great Berber Revolt" of 122/740 in eastern and western historiographical sources, particularly their attribution of responsibility for the loss of the far West. She shows that although the interpretation of events varies depending on the author's position, all sources marginalize the "Berber" local protagonists and adhere to a pre-determined view of their character and relation to the Empire. The next article by Elsa CARDOSO investigates the rituals, titles, and metaphors used in the Umayyad court of Cordoba for the caliphs (many of them with astrological imaginary), as well as the epithets applied to opponents to the regime. She shows that the reference to eastern Umayyads was a central pillar of their claim to caliphal legitimacy and was regularly enacted in the court ceremonial.

The use of memory as a legitimizing motif by the western Umayyads is pursued further in Jorge ELICES OCÓN's article, which examines the biography of various objects that travelled as spolia between the Islamic West and East. He investigates how stories about these objects served as legitimizing instruments to underpin claims of hegemony on the part of the rulers. His article leads well into Eduardo MANZANO MORENO's contribution, which explores the unusual funerary practices of the western Umayyad dynasty, merging the role of memory in material culture and symbolic rituals. He focuses on references in written sources to an *intra muros* cemetery of the royal palace in Cordoba, called *rawḍa* (garden, orchard), and highlights not only the images of Quranic Paradise that this name evokes but also the parallels with the Prophet's Mosque in Medina. As he shows, it is interesting to relate this conceptualization to efforts to vindicate the tainted memory of the Umayyads as it had been constructed by their archenemies the Abbasids. Finally, the article by Isabel TORAL studies the depiction of Mu'āwiya and 'Abd al-Malik in the *ʿIqd al-Farīd* (a literary encyclopedia composed during the western Umayyad caliphate) and shows how the examples of these prominent eastern Umayyad

ancestors were not only framed as models of rigorous leadership, decisiveness, and a pragmatic approach to politics but also as a deterrent to potential opponents and a call for unity.

The contributions showcase how the idea of caliphal Umayyad continuity between East to West came to be imagined as the transfer of the caliphal authority from Syria to the Iberian Peninsula, or a veritable *translatio Imperii*. As such, this idea played a central role in the legitimation of the dynasty in al-Andalus. They also show that the shared eastern–western Umayyad memory continued to exercise a powerful hold over the historical consciousness of its successors. Like the ‘Abbāsid caliphate after 1258, the Umayyad caliphate survived its own disappearance for many centuries, in reminiscences of past glory, in shadows of defeat, in claims for legitimacy, and in the political call for unity and Islamic strength.

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